

Coordination Complexes of Some Group (IV) Halides with Pyrazine Amides

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Manuscript received 1 March 1976; accepted 22 April 1976

Co-ordination compounds of group (IV) halides, MX_4 ($M = Ti, Zr$ or $Sn, X = Cl$ or Br) with the ligands 2-pyrazine carboxamide (pyza) and 2, 3 pyrazine dicarboxamide (pyzda) have been prepared and characterised. Adducts of the type $MX_4 \cdot pyza$, $3 MX_4 \cdot 2 pyza$, $2 MX_4 \cdot pyzda$ and $MX_4 \cdot pyzda$ have been obtained under different experimental conditions. The infrared spectral investigations in the region ($4000-650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) have been carried out to determine the coordination sites and the possible structures of the compounds.

IN continuation of our studies of the complexes of groups (IV) and (V) metal halides with nitrogen and oxygen containing ligands¹⁻⁴, work on the reactions of some of the group (IV) halides with 2-pyrazine carboxamide (pyza) and 2,3 pyrazine dicarboxamide (pyzda) has been carried out to study the ligating behaviour of the pyrazine nitrogens and the amide group present on the same ligand molecule. Pyrazines⁵⁻⁷ and amides^{8,9} have been extensively used as ligands. Though pyrazine is potentially a bridging bidentate ligand, recent work on its complexation with transition metal halides suggests that it can act as monodentate ligand bonded through one of its ring nitrogens. With pyza and pyzda in particular, it is of interest to explore the possibility of obtaining five membered chelate compounds involving the hetero-cyclic ring nitrogen and one of the amide donor atoms, oxygen or nitrogen.

Experimental

The chemicals $TiCl_4$, $TiBr_4$, $SnCl_4$ and $ZrCl_4$ were purified by suitable methods. The ligands were obtained from commercial sources and were used as such without further purification. The solvents methylene chloride, 1,2-dichloroethane and tetrahydrofuran were treated with appropriate drying agents and fractionally distilled before use.

Since the Lewis acids used and their complexes are highly sensitive to atmospheric moisture, all the experimental manipulations were carried out in a dry box continuously flushed with dry nitrogen and maintained dry by means of phosphorus(V) oxide. The experimental set up and general methods of preparation of complexes were reported previously^{2,4}. Stoichiometries of the reactants and the solvents used for the preparation of the compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL RESULTS

Compound	Amounts of		Solvent of adduct	Colour	Melting Point °C	Metal % calc. found	Halogen % calc. found	Nature of adduct
	Halide	m Mole Ligand						
$TiCl_4 \cdot pyza$	9.12		CH_2Cl_2	Yellow	270 D	15.31	45.33	1 : 1
	8.32							
$3TiCl_4 \cdot 2 \cdot pyza$	18.24		"	"	215 D	17.62	52.18	3 : 2
	6.82							
$TiBr_4 \cdot pyza$	5.90			Red	220 D	10.76	65.16	1 : 1
	5.90							
$ZrCl_4 \cdot pyza$	8.58		THF	Pale	200 D	25.65	39.83	1 : 1
	8.13							
$SnCl_4 \cdot pyza$	10.18		CH_2Cl_2	White	250 D	30.97	36.13	1 : 1
	10.00							
$2 TiCl_4 \cdot pyzda$	18.24		"	Yellow	190 D	17.97	51.98	2 : 1
	5.62							
$TiBr_4 \cdot pyzda$	5.90		"	Red	215 D	8.90	59.90	1 : 1
	2.65							
$SnCl_4 \cdot pyzda$	10.25		"	White	235	27.84	33.25	1 : 1
	4.14							

pyza = 2-pyrazine carboxamide
pyzda = 2, 3-pyrazine dicarboxamide
D = Decomposed by turning black

The metals and halogens were determined by conventional analytical methods. The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer model 21 and Perkin Elmer infracord, in Nujol mulls using NaCl optics.

Results and Discussion

Pyza Complexes: Substitution of a carboxamide group on a pyrazine ring makes 2-pyrazine carboxamide an interesting chelating ligand. It can conveniently coordinate to a metal atom through one of the hetero cyclic nitrogens and one of the side chain donor atoms, forming a five-membered chelate, I or II.

In the case of amide complexes, the frequencies most often discussed^{11,12} in the i.r. spectra, in order to determine the site of bonding, are $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$, $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$. It is reported^{8,9,12} that when an amide is coordinated through oxygen, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ normally decreases by 30–80 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ shows a positive shift as compared to those of the free ligand. The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ has been reported to increase for some complexes^{11,13} and decrease for others. In fact, this band should decrease regardless of the nature of attachment. If coordination of an amide to the metal takes place through nitrogen then, an increase in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and decrease in $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ would be expected.

The i.r. spectra (Table 2) of the 1:1 adducts of TiCl_4 , TiBr_4 , and ZrCl_4 with pyza show negative shifts in the range of 63–48 cm^{-1} in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ as compared to that of the uncoordinated ligand. In the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ region, two bands at 1195 and 1172 cm^{-1} for the free ligand appear in the higher frequency region for the complexes. Gerrad *et al.*¹¹ and Faron and coworkers¹² have critically analysed the effect of coordination of an amide group on $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ bands. They have concluded that the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ is weakened upon coordination through either nitrogen or oxygen and as a result of this, a decrease in the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ bands is expected.

In the present study, the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ show a general tendency of shifting to lower frequency regions on complexation. The NH_2 -deformation band at 1632 cm^{-1} of the free ligand also shifts to lower region by about 40 cm^{-1} . These changes in the infrared spectra are in conformity with the coordination of the amide group through the carbonyl group.

In the case of pyrazine and 2,6 dimethyl pyrazine complexes with group(IV) halides Fowles and Walton⁶ have reported $\text{MX}_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$ type of adducts.

They have shown that the i.r. active bands at 960 and 1160 cm^{-1} for the ligands appear only, if one of the nitrogens is coordinated. When both the nitrogens are taking part in coordination, these bands do not appear in the spectra.

As can be seen from Table 1, pyza forms 1:1 and 3:2 types of adducts with TiCl_4 and 1:1 adducts with TiBr_4 , ZrCl_4 and SnCl_4 . In general, the infrared spectra of the 1:1 adducts are similar and invariably show two bands at about 940 and 980 cm^{-1} . According to Lever *et al.*^{5abc}, a band in the 950–1000 cm^{-1} region is characteristic of the monodentate nature of pyrazine in its complexes. From the above observation, it can be implied that in the 1:1 adducts one heterocyclic nitrogen and the adjacent carbonyl oxygen are involved in coordination forming 5-membered chelate (III).

Similar 5-membered chelates have been proposed by Sutton^{14,15} with 2-thioamide pyridine with various Lewis acids.

The spectrum of 3 TiCl_4 , 2 pyza differs from the spectra of the 1:1 adducts in the region 950–1000 cm^{-1} . The absence of any band in this region can be attributed to coordination through both the heterocyclic nitrogens of the ligand molecules. The lowering of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ for the compound as compared to the free ligand (Table 2) further indicate coordination through the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups, also. Since this compound was obtained by reacting the ligand with excess of TiCl_4 , the probable course of reaction seems to be via the formation of 1:1 complex, two molecules of which further coordinate, to a molecule of TiCl_4 through the available ring nitrogens. On the basis of stoichiometry of the compound and the i.r. results, it is therefore, suggested that this compound consists of two 5-membered chelates and a bridging titanium tetrachloride molecule (IV).

An X-ray investigation¹⁶ of dibromo 2-5 methyl pyrazine Ni(II) has also confirmed that pyrazine can form bonds at each end coordinating to two different metal atoms.

TABLE 2. INFRARED SPECTRA (cm^{-1}) OF 2-PYRAZINE CARBOXAMIDE (PYZA) AND ITS COMPLEXES

Pyza	TiCl ₄ .pyza	3TiCl ₄ .2pyza	TiBr ₄ .pyza	ZrCl ₄ .pyza	SnCl ₄ .pyza	band ^{12, 17} assignments
		3550 s				
3520 s	3450 m	3448 m	3425 s	3440 sh	3450 sh	} $\nu(\text{N-H})$
3360 m	3350 sh	3335 s	3330 m	3320 m	3350 m	
3244 s	3240 m	3210 sh	3215 m	3230 m	3180 ms	
1738 vs	1675 vs	1694 vs 1654 sh	1685 vs	1685 m	1690 vs	$\nu(\text{C=O})$
1632 s	1595 m	1610 m	1612 w	1585 s	1590 vw	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$
1601 ms	1580 m	1580 m	1575 m	1560 sh	1580 m	} $\nu(\text{C=N})$
1536 w	1502 sh	1505 sh	1508 m	1505 m	1459 s	
1320 vw	1316 m	1320 m	1323 w	1340 m	1313 m	
1195 m	1270 w	1220 m	1279 w	1250 w	1250 m	} $\nu(\text{C-N})$
1172 s	1187 ms	1182 m	1190 ms	1180 w	1185 s	
—	1150 m	1145 m	1156 w	1150 w	1150 m	
1105 m	1105 s	1105 m	1105 m	1110 w	1105 sh	} Hydrogen bends
1058 s	1070 s	1068 s	1064 m	1060 w	1082 s	
1034 s	1050 sb	—	1053 s	1050 w	1050 m	} Ring vibration
—	970 w	—	980 w	980 w	1018 s	
—	944 m	—	943 w	950 w	980 w, 957 w	
874 s	864 m	864 m	866 m	860 vw	860 w	} (C-H) out of plane bending.
810 sh	825 m	810 m	822 m	820 sh	820 s	
790 s	780 m	780 ms	780 m	785 s	785 w	
760 w	748 m	760 m	741 m	740 m	740 s	

v = very, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, sh = shoulder, b = broad.

Pyza Complexes: The ligand 2,3-pyrazine dicarboxamide has two amide groups which can independently form two chelates involving both the heterocyclic nitrogens and side chain donor atoms. In the reaction of TiCl₄ with pyza, a 2 : 1 adduct was obtained, whereas ZrCl₄ and SnCl₄ formed 1 : 1 type of adducts (Table 1).

In the i.r. spectrum (Table 3) of the 2 : 1 compound, the $\nu(\text{C=O})$, $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ show lowering of 40, 52 and 100 cm^{-1} respectively as compared to the corresponding bands of the free ligand. The absence of any band in the region 950–1000 cm^{-1} (the appearance of which is characteristic of the monodentate nature of the ligand) in the spectrum of the complex can be due to the involvement of either both or none of the heterocyclic nitrogens in coordination. In case both the ring nitrogens are involved in coordi-

nation, the structure of the compound would consist of two 5-membered chelates (V)

V

The non-involvement of the ring nitrogens would suggest a halide bridging structure satisfying the

most probable coordination number of six for titanium; (VI)

VI

It is interesting to note that the two bands at 1558 and 1586 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ in the spectrum of the ligand do not appear in this region for the complex. This suggests strong perturbation of the ring vibrations due to the involvement of both the ring nitrogens in coordination, and thus favouring chelate structure for the compound.

Similar to the spectrum of the 2 : 1 adduct, the spectra of the 1 : 1 adducts, also do not show any band in the region 950–1000 cm^{-1} and indicate the involvement of both the carbonyl groups in coordination. Whereas, contrary to the 2 : 1 adduct, bands due to ring vibrations $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ appear in the region 1530–1570 cm^{-1} for the 1 : 1 adducts. This suggests the non-involvement of the ring nitrogens in coordination. In such situation, the two C=O groups can either coordinate to the same or to two different metal atoms forming a monomeric or polymeric compounds; VII or VIII.

Such an arrangement would impart a coordination number of six to each metal atom. Because of the poor solubility of these compounds in suitable inert solvents, the molecular weights and molar conductance could not be determined to ascertain whether

TABLE 3. INFRARED SPECTRA (cm^{-1}) OF 2, 3-PYRAZINE DICARBOXAMIDE (PYZDA) AND ITS COMPLEXES

Pyzda	2TiCl ₄ . pyzda	TiBr ₄ . pyzda	SnCl ₄ . pyzda	band assignments ^{12,17}
3550 s	3450 s	3448 m	3478 vs	} $\nu(\text{N-H})$
3390 vs	3280 sh	3333 m	3355 s	
3283 s	3218 s	3240 sh	3330 s	
1710 vs	1670 vs	1675 vs	1680 vs	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$
1632 s	1570 s	1584 m	1575 ms	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$
1586 ms	—	1570 sh	1550 ms	} $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$
1558 sh	—	1504 m	1500 s	
—	—	1430 sh	1422 s	} $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$
1409 m	—	1408 m	1410 m	
1360 ms	1360 sh	1360 sh	1360 sh	
—	—	1260 w	1260 m	} $\nu(\text{C-N})$
1201 m	1222 w	1232 m	1230 m	
—	—	—	1210 m	
1172 w	1172 w	1179 w, 1160 m	1178 sh, 1160 ms	
1105 vs	1128 s	1120 s	1110 vs	} Hydrogen bends.
1080 mw	1100 m	1100 sh	1090 sh	
1066 ms	1066 m	1073 m	1070 s	Ring vibration
883 s	884 mw	889 vw	885 s	} C-H out of plane bending.
860 s	866 mw	866 mb	866 s	
800 w	—	813 vw	812 w	
760 s	750 sh	758 m	758 vs	
740 sb	748 s	738 m	742 m	

v = very, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, sh = shoulder, oulder, b = broad.

VIII

the compounds are monomeric or polymeric in nature. However, their poor solubility and higher decomposition temperatures indicate that these compounds may be polymeric in nature.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. D. Karkhana-
vala, Head, Chemistry Division, for encouragement
during the course of this work. Thanks are also due
to Dr. H. S. Ahuja for helpful discussions.

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